

7-H, vicinal to lactone), 3.16 (1H, s, 9H), 1.69 (3H, s, 10-CH₃), 4.05 (1H, d, 3H z, 12H), 1.39 (3H, d, 13-CH₃), 6.14 (1H, d, 11Hz, 15-H, vicinal to ester function), 4.19 and 3.62 (each 1H, d, 18.5Hz, 17 CH₂-O, hemiketal), 1.22 (3H, d, 2'-CH₃) and 1.07 (3H, t, CH₃CH₂). Although molecular ion peak is reported² for this compound but no such peak was discernible in the spectrum of the compound isolated by us. On the contrary mass fragment ions appear at *m/e* 462, C₂₈H₃₄O₈ (M⁺-H₂O); 361, C₂₀H₂₅O₆ (462-101 mass units of the C₈ acid side chain); 360, C₂₀H₂₄O₆; 231, C₁₄H₁₈O₈; 85, C₄H₆O; 57, C₄H₆ (base peak).

The ¹³C nmr spectrum of excelsin is very similar to that of glaucarubin³ from which it differs only in the nature of the side chain. The chemical shifts of glaucarubin and the chemical shift and multiplicities (obtained from the Sford spectra and denoted in parenthesis) of excelsin are depicted in Table 1.

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Quercetin-3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside from Root of *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall.

S. K. CHATURVEDI and V. K. SAXENA
Chemical Laboratories,

Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 28 November 1983, revised 12 July 1984,
accepted 18 January 1985

ANOGEISSUS latifolia Wall. (N.O. Comberataceae) is a medicinal plant^{1,2} which is distributed throughout the greater part of India. Because of its great medicinal importance, its phytochemical investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

The roots of *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall. (4 kg) collected from the forest of Patharia Hills, Sagar (authenticated by the Department of Botany of this University) were powdered and extracted with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The defatted roots were extracted with 95% ethanol, and the ethanol extract concentrated under reduced pressure to a brown viscous mass was resolved into water-soluble and water-insoluble parts. The water-soluble part was concentrated and successively extracted with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone. The chloroform-soluble part gave the glycoside which was purified by passing over a column of silica gel G and crystallised as yellow needles

with petrol-benzene, m.p. 272-74°. The homogeneity of the glycoside was checked by paper chromatography in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5), R_f 0.34, yield 0.052%.

Results and Discussion

The glycoside, m.p. 272-74°, showed positive Shinoda test for flavonoid. Hydrolysis of the glycoside with ethanolic sulphuric acid (7%) afforded an aglycone and the sugars identified as D-galactose and L-rhamnose (by co-pc, co-tlc).

The aglycone crystallised from petrol-chloroform as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 212-14° (Found : C, 59.62; H, 3.31. C₁₅H₁₀O₇ requires C, 59.60; H, 3.33%). The structure to the aglycone was assigned as 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavone (quercetin) by m.m.p., degradative studies and spectral analysis and is a well known compound.

The hydrolysability of the glycoside with almond emulsion³ yielding D-galactose, the first appearance of D-galactose on partial hydrolysis (1% H₂SO₄), consumption of 3.02 mole of periodate⁴ with the production of 1.3 mole of formic acid per mole of the glycoside; acid hydrolysis of the permethylated glycoside⁵ (DMS/dry K₂CO₃ yielding 2,3-di-O-methyl-α-L-rhamnose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-β-D-galactose (by co-pc and co-tlc) indicated the sugar moiety to be β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside attached to C-3-free OH group present in the aglycone. Attachment of sugar residue at C-3 was further supported by uv shift. The aglycone as well as the glycoside showed the presence of free OH groups at C-3' and C-4' (uv shift upon addition of AlCl₃/H₃BO₃)⁶, at C-5 and C-7 (uv shift with AlCl₃ and CH₃COONa)⁷, while C-3 OH was present in the aglycone (yellow fluorescence in uv light)⁸ and absence in the glycoside (no yellow fluorescence), thus confirming the structure of the glycoside as quercetin-3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside, further supported by nmr spectrum, δ 7.35 (d, 2.5 H_z, H-2'), 7.65 (dd, 2.5 and 9H_z, H-6), 7.0 (d, 9H_z, H-5'), 6.50 (d, 2.4 H_z, H-6), 6.53 (d, 2H_z, H-8), 5.47 (d, 2H_z, 1' H, anomeric proton of rhamnose), 0.78 (d, 6H_z, methyl group of rhamnose), 4.9 (d, 7H_z, 1'' H, anomeric proton of galactose), 3.5-3.7 (m, 6 protons of galactosyl unit) 2.35-2.49 (s, 4×OAc aromatic and 2.09-2.21 (6×OAc sugar acyl group).

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu for spectral analysis and one of the authors (S.K.C.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for awarding Senior Research Fellowship.

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Isolation of Hordenine from *Desmodium floribundum* G. Don.

R. MAURYA, M. SAHAI†

and

A. B. RAY*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, I.M.S.,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 18 April 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

DESMODIUM (Leguminosae) is a large genus of perennial or annual herbs or shrubs found throughout the tropical and subtropical regions of the world. About thirtyeight species belonging to this genus are known to occur in India^{1,2}. The extracts of different parts of the members of this genus are well known for their medicinal uses in the indigenous system of medicine for a variety of ailments¹.

Earlier work on the alkaloids of a number of *Desmodium* species by Ghosal and coworkers* shows that this genus elaborates mainly simple indole and β -phenylethylamine alkaloids some of which elicit interesting pharmacodynamic properties. In view of this observation and the absence of any published report on the alkaloids of *Desmodium floribundum*, this plant was collected from Ranikhet (U.P.) area and taken up for investigation of its alkaloids. Separation of alkaloids from the alcoholic extract of the whole plant of *D. floribundum* following usual procedure⁴, chromatography of the total alkaloid fraction over silica gel column and elution with ethyl acetate-methanol (97 : 3) mixture furnished a homogenous solid which crystallised from benzene as colourless plates, m.p. 173°. The compound responded to Beilstein test for halogens, phosphomolybdic acid test for phenols and analysed for the molecular formula, C₁₀H₁₅NO.HCl. Its uv spectrum (λ_{\max} 224, 227 nm; ϵ 7330, 2200) resembled that of *p*-cresol, its spectrum showed band for phenolic hydroxyl (3450 cm⁻¹) and ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃ + CD₃OD) showed signals for four aromatic hydrogens of a 1,4-disubstituted phenyl nucleus (δ 7.11 and 6.78, 2H, d each, J 8Hz), four aliphatic hydrogens of two vicinal methylenes around δ 3.14 as multiplets and two methyl groups bound to a protonated nitrogen as a six-proton singlet at δ 2.89. Mass spectrum of the compound showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 165 (4%) corresponding to

the free base, C₁₀H₁₅NO, a significant ion peak at *m/z* 107 (9%) due to hydroxytropylium cation and the base peak at *m/z* 58 (CH₂=N⁺Me₂) characteristic of dimethylaminoethyl side chain⁵. The data indicated the alkaloid to be hordenine hydrochloride (*N,N*-dimethyltyramine hydrochloride) which was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p. and tlc) of the derived free base with authentic sample.

The notoriety of chloroform for conversion of alkamines to their hydrochlorides is well known^{6,7} and the isolation of hordenine as its hydrochloride is presumably due to the use of this solvent for extraction of alkaloids.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance, to Prof. Paul L. Schiff, Jr., School of Pharmacy, University of Pittsburgh, U.S.A. for mass spectrum, to Prof. S. Ghosal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, for an authentic sample of hordenine and to the Amalgamated Unit of C.C.R.A.S., Tarikhet, Ranikhet for identification of plant material.

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Chemistry of *Salvia lanata* Roxb.

K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. K. GHOSH

and

R. K. MUKHERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati,
Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 30 April 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

IN previous communications¹⁻³, we reported the isolation and characterisation of some di- and tri-terpenoidal components from the petrol extract of the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Salvia lanata*⁴. This paper reports the isolation and identification of three pentacyclic triterpenes from the chloroform extract of defatted plant materials. Air dried and powdered whole plant (aerial parts

†The Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot, Israel.